

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B096
Date: 19 May 2005
Take Off 09:52:58
Landing: 14:31:04
Flight Time 4h38m06

Campaign: CWVC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Chilbolton Radar

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Charlie Whittaker	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Flight Manager Training	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	CCN /CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	SID2 Diagnostics 1	Edwin Hirst	University of Hertfordshire
9	SID2 Diagnostics 2	Richard Greenaway	University of Hertfordshire
10	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
11	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
12	CPI	Paul Connolly	University of Manchester
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B096 Track 19-MAY-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b096
 Date: 19 May 2005
 Project: CWVC
 Location: Chilboten

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
093406		INU to nav	0.33 kft	115	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
093806		taxy start	0.32 kft	115	
093819		taxy start	0.32 kft	117	
095258		T/O	0.31 kft	211	from cranfield
100223		asp open	6.0 kft	218	
100636		jw zero	6.0 kft	184	
102056	105933	Profile 1	3.7 - 30.0 kft	251	
103442		Profile 1	17.0 kft	252	interrupt
103833		Profile 1	17.0 kft	082	resume
104911		Profile 1	27.0 kft	077	interrupt
105515		Profile 1	27.2 kft	259	resume
111048	111447	Run 1	23.0 kft	075	
112245	112902	Run 2	20.0 kft	253	
113725	114256	Run 3	10.5 kft	076	
114737	120012	Run 4	10.0 kft	235	
120515	121156	Run 5	9.0 kft	076	
121513	121617	Profile 2.1	9.0 - 10.0 kft	261	
121618	121724	Profile 2.2	10.0 - 9.1 kft	243	
121725	121926	Run 6	9.1 - 9.0 kft	252	
121926	122023	Profile 3.1	9.0 - 8.0 kft	251	
122023	122129	Profile 3.2	8.0 - 9.0 kft	253	
122129	122332	Run 7	9.0 kft	252	
122332	122432	Profile 4.1	9.0 - 9.9 kft	251	
122432	122543	Profile 4.2	9.9 - 9.1 kft	249	
122543	122749	Run 8	9.1 - 9.0 kft	250	
123326	123634	Profile 5.1	9.0 - 12.0 kft	078	
123634	123745	Profile 5.2	12.0 - 11.0 kft	077	
123745	123949	Run 9	11.0 kft	081	
124311	124422	Profile 6.1	11.0 - 10.1 kft	254	
124422	124830	Profile 6.2	10.1 - 14.0 kft	248	
124830	125055	Run 10	14.0 kft	252	
125135	125547	Profile 7	14.0 - 10.1 kft	251	
130007	130516	Profile 7.2	10.0 - 5.0 kft	087	
130616	130833	Run 11	5.0 kft	077	
131154	131451	Profile 8	5.0 - 8.0 kft	266	
131451	132458	Run 12	8.0 kft	250	
132846	133104	Profile 9	8.0 - 10.0 kft	084	
133105	133656	Run 13	10.0 kft	078	
134027	134659	Profile 10	10.0 - 15.9 kft	252	
135045	135500	Run 14	16.0 kft	090	
140835		asp closed	5.0 kft	351	
143104		Land	0.35 kft	308	Cranfield
		Apron 2			52 04.36N 000 35.50W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B096 Track 19-MAY-05

PROJECT BRIEF: CWVC – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems that lie within the temperature regime in which mixed-phase clouds are possible (typically 0 to -30C). In particular, we wish to examine the competing roles of

- primary ice nucleation
- secondary nucleation via the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of larger ice particles.
- other secondary ice nucleation mechanisms such as evaporative break-up
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamical environment within the cloud (and in particular the strength of embedded convective updraughts)

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the Camra radar facility at Chilbolton, Hants. The radar may identify features such as embedded convective cells or layers of supercooled liquid water that can be investigated more intensively by the aircraft. Similarly, the aircraft can provide information on microphysical characteristics to aid interpretation of the radar data.

Weather conditions: A stratiform cloud band lying over or to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction, and hence to more easily penetrate identifiable cloud features on successive runs at the same altitude. Note that to avoid interference with Bournemouth airport, Chilbolton is NOT allowed to transmit in the sector 209 to 219 degrees true.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 (and SID-2). Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- ADA/CPI – as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest.
- Ice Nucleus counter (INC) will normally be operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to a different set of conditions.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.

Sortie Brief: CWVC – mixed-phase cloud studies

Flight Number: Bnnn

Date: 19 May 2005

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes and cloud dynamics in stratiform cloud systems in association with Chilbolton radar.

Sortie Location: Within a stratiform cloud system over or to the west of Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (127.050 MHz, call-sign “Radsearch”). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. In this case, the aircraft may fly a small butterfly pattern in which only one of the legs is parallel to the wind direction or radar azimuth. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles. On occasion, the aircraft flight legs may start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace.

Sortie Detail:

- a) T+0 Take off and climb to FL200 for transit to the operating area west of Chilbolton.
- b) T+40 When in a suitable location, perform a profile descent at 1000ft/min from FL200 to 1000ft agl or 1000 ft below the freezing level, whichever is the lower (20 min)
- c) T+60 Establish start/end points of 40-80km flight leg along the azimuth which is being scanned by the radar. Fly this leg at altitudes defined by the radar. Duration of each leg ~ 5-10 minutes. Some legs may be extended into the overhead position of Chilbolton when requested from the ground.
- d) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern (see diagram)

- e) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level and with level segments of 1 minute.
- f) Items c) to e) may be repeated as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci K.N. BOWER

CWVC

Flight No **B.096**.....

Date **19/05/05**.....

Page **1**..... of **6**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:03:04	T	6000'	196	51.9N/1.4W	Clear Air CCN sample taken - approx 15 mins at 6000'
10:07:50	T				descending to 5000' ATC
10:09:26	T	5000	193	51.6/1.4W	New level reached
10:14:50	T	5000	192	51.3/1.4	Drizzle getting big 800-1000m CPT
10:17:14		5000			Descending to 3500' for start P1
					(Remaining along 1 st Radial - will start P1 at 3500')
10:20:56	P1 start	3500'			P1 (to 240'00) on -EW leg
10:24:12	P1	7100'	250		1.67°C / -11.03°C 12m/s/221 deg 766mb
		8700'			Radar ⇒ turbo at 2.5km 8200' - windshear?
		9400'			a little turbulence -
10:29		11,500'			Photo Front Right
					(M.Sci / Flight Sci - B&3)
10:29:50		13420			Photo ahead - Ci above.
10:33:20		15500	252		-14.86 -21.61
10:34:10					Ice ahead, low N, CPT, 2D contain this
10:34:22	P1 int	17000			(MODIS O/P - Ci are around + S. - ppt around is quite small -
10:36:56	P1 int	17000	turn continues		to turn onto a W-E P1 leg. -16.71/-17.97°C
					14m/s/248° 526 mb.
10:38:33	P1 retransmitting	FL170			clear air W-E leg.
					azimuth 253° True.
		25000			35.
					worked on radar 5km alt
10:41:11	P1 int	27000'			Intermittent - left them back on E-W leg.

7000 221°
17000 244°

Ci ice ahead - rather than where we are - difficult to pick up

Mission Scientist's Log

Misc K.N. BOWER CWVC

Flight No **B.096**.....

Date 19/05/05.....

Page 2 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					shut runs 40km from Chilbolton
					FL 230 in Cirrus
10:55:15	P1	FL 270			Profile P1 resumed
10:59:33	P1 end	F300	257		35m/s / 264° -47.53 / -48.88°C 302mb
11:00:40			256	51.04/2.1W	photo in descent - off to right
	R1 start	23000		51.0 / 2.4W	Inbound to Chilbolton - looking for Ci
					(2DC few particles - CPI - seeing particles)
					(Q-Radar - Plume over Chilbolton)
					Cloud - gradually lowering 4½ km - 7½ km
					14000 - 24000 - shut runs desc to
					Chilbolton - 5-6 km 19-20,000'
					length of legs - shorter the better 20-25k
					12½ miles from Chilbolton
					20 mile legs
11:10:48	R1 start	FL 230			
11:14:47	R1 end	FL 230			CPI - 2D seeing particles
11:17:50					last 1 minute seeing Ci partial (2D/CPI)
					Ci - above us now
11:22:45	R2	FL 200			- No cloud here -
					(10-14000 ish - good belt - says run 13000)
					(Captain
					Cloud - 5-7km breaking up
					Subsided H ₂ O - 12,500 -
11:29:02	R2 end	FL 200			Capt - abandons run - heading E-W - descend
					to 13000, to do W-E run SLE to Chil.

shut runs

50

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci: K.N. BOWER CWVC

Flight No **B.096**.....

Date 19/5/05.....

Page 3 of 6...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:35:08					No cloud at 13000' → 11000'
	R	FL110			Inbound - still no cloud (-5.24/-18.9°C 20/228')
11:37:25	R3 ↓	FL105			10500' 60km out
11:40:46	R3	FL105	80°	51.0/1.9W	Seeing small drops -4.0/-8.5° 21/234 20sec out -
11:42:40	R				
11:42:56	R3 end	FL105			(P. Down actv) - terminate run
11:47:57	R4 st	FL100	240	51.1/1.5W	West away from Chil -3.03/-2.93°C 19m/s/21
11:49:09	R4	FL100		51.1/1.6W	CP7 water small particles + water ← 2D
11:50:45	R4		251	51.0/1.8W	bumps -3.28/-3.23 18m/s/221° 696mb only seen LW - no ice CP7 solar horiz run
11:52:15	R4				2D - only Water.
11:54:13			250	50.9/2.2W	Aircraft - seen on radar - v clear -
12:00:12	R4 end				and descends
12:09:15	R5	FL090			(20041s) True MS 234, Indicated 200
12:08:17	R5	FL090	77	51.0/2.1	723mb: -2.17/-1.14 18m/s/228
12:11:56	R5 end				only LWC
					see echos 3h - 60-70-8h -
					closed 10 mls - 60 mls
12:15:	P2.1				descent 1000' in scrubth - to FL100
12:16:17	P2.2				descent 1000' to FL90
12:17:24	R6	FL090			
12:19:36	P3.1				end R6, stop - (at base T _v 0°/-10°C)
	P3.2				45km Outbound
12:21:29	R7	FL090			-1.77/-0.65

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci K.N. BOWER

CWVC

Flight No **B.096**.....

Date 19/05/05.....

Page 4 of 6.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:23:32	P4.1				climb 1000' to 10000
12:24:32	P4.2				descent 1000' to 9000'
12:25:43	R8 st	FL90			
					very extensive cloud over 80km layer
					10000 - 12000' where thick layer
12:27:49	R8 end				cloud SIC water unheated from rad ⁿ part of view
					Broadband radiometer level flight above
12:33:26	PS start	FL90 ↑	78	50.9/2.4	9000 ↑ -2.87 -3.98°C, 19 m/s/226, 675.1
12:36:34	end PS/P5.2		76	51.0/2.0	FL120 ↓ -6.16, -37.81 17/233
	P5.2	11200'			661
12:37:45	P5.2 end/R9	FL110	80	51.0/1.9W	Bumpy
12:39:49	R9 end/turn	FL110	140	51.0/1.7	22/224° -5.03 9.06 669.25
					Radar - current SIC layer - peaking out at 70km range - Pilot ✓
12:43:	P6.1	FL110 → 100	242	51.1/1.6W	Proble descent to FL100 681mb -4.0/5.6
12:44:22	P6.2	FL100-110	248	51.0/1.7W	680mb -4.69/4.97 17m/s/220
					CPI - all LW all saw - 2D too
12:47:09	P6.2		251	51.0/2.0W	-7.12 / -36.19 16/227 680mb
12:48:30	R10	14000'			end P6.2
12:50:55	R10 end	FL140			descent to ~ 6-7000'
12:51:35	P7 start				
12:53:06	P7	descent	251	50.9/2.4	-8.32 / -27.25 17/240' 672mb
					-seeing thick cloud above

descent ↑ 14000

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci - K.N. BOWEN CNVC

Flight No **B.096**

Date **19/03/05**

Page **5** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:55:42	P7 int	FL100			intermittent - beam
13:00:07	P7 recon	FL100 ↓	85	50.9/26	recommencing P7 down to FL50
13:00:55	P7	~9200			-1.15°C / -20.26 18 m/s / 237° 716 mb
13:03:55	P7	6800	76	50.9/23	Cloud tops.
13:05:16	P7 end	FL5000			
13:06:16	R11st				Large droplets - 2D - CPI was seeing large droplets
13:08	R11 end				beam - profile clouds to FL80
13:10:12					SD in range - 1 km high - Radar sees in.
13:11:00					Arriving CB - broad section - large / small droplets
					2D same (just prior to this)
13:11:54	P8 st	FL50 ↑	264	51.0/17W	+4.2/2.1°C 12 m/s / 232° 816 mb.
13:14:51	P8 end / P12 start	FL60	250	51.0/19W	-0.05/0.08 18 m/s / 220° 752
					Cloud gap -
					Radar → after this run below cloud - middle layer
					@ 10000' - to check cloud is same
13:19:27	R12	FL80	250	50.9/2.3W	Photo of cloud gap
13:21:00	R12				In cloud again - tops of lower level.
13:24:58	R12 end	@ FL80			terminating to do profile ascent
					intermittent interpen on frequency
	P9 start				
	P9	7	72°		
13:31:05	end P9				-1.89/19.01
13:34:16					seen few - 10s with ice crystals
13:36:56	end fan	13 FL100			we were not on cloud so attempting to do Ci above - then
13:40:27	end P10				profile to 16000

35

E-W

N-E

E-W

extension - best high echo Ci - 60-70 km 5 km 16000'
 radar - in beam 16000 - 8 km range

range end 80 km
 height - 5 km
 10-15000

FLIGHT NUMBER	B096	DATE:	19/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CWVC					

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	OK
All cylinders pressures are OK	OK
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	OK

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	500 psi	130	130
POST FLIGHT	400 psi	130	130

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.35	0.4	1.108	0.068	0.479
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
OK	34.10	1.07	7.15	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-1	-2	-1	-3	-2	-1	
NO (ppbV)	0.07	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.08	0.09	
NO₂ (ppbV)	1.44	1.47	1.51	1.56	1.59	1.61	
NO_x (ppbV)	1.66	1.61	1.55	1.50	1.51	1.7	
SO₂ (ppbV)	-2.91	-1.91	-2.36	-2.61	-1.91	-2.36	

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS
CO took a long time to warm up – not warmed up by security check

FLIGHT NUMBER	B096	DATE:	19/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CWVC					

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL		Date and Flight Level		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)							
		19/5/05 HANGAR		82.95		87.11		7226.01							
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		89.89		83.04		7464.61		45.49		7.15					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample					
10:17:23		5000ft		34		0.7		0.8		0.068		1.204		0.431	
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		86.74		81.90		7103.34		48.08		7.15					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample					
10:37:46:		170		34.01		0.7		0.8		1.042		0.064		ALARM	
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		84.24		82.48		6948.29		49.64		7.14					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample					
10:51:54		270		33.91		0.7		0.75		0.971		0.067		ALARM	
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		82.77		82.85		6857.57		50.0		7.13					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample					
11:07:39		230		33.96		0.7		0.75		0.998		0.066		ALARM	
Time	Flight Level	CO													
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgrd (ppbV)		Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)		Lamp Temp (°C)		Cell Press (Torr)					
		82.13		83.04		6820.33		50		7.14					
		Flows (LPM unless stated)													
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)		Ozone Sample 1		Ozone Sample 2		NO _x Sample		NO _x Ozonator		SO ₂ Sample					
11:25:40		200		33.95		0.7		0.75		1.032		0.064		ALARM	

FLIGHT NUMBER	B096	DATE:	19/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CWVC					

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

Time	Flight Level	CO						
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
11:38:38	110	81.98	84.41	6919.93	50	7.12		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)						
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		33.93	0.7	0.75	OK	OK	ALARM	
12:07:56		CO						
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
		81.85	84.08	6882.20	50	7.14		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)						
13:11:54		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		33.88	0.7	0.75	OK	OK	OK	
		13:34:12	100	CO				
				Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
81.04	84.21			6824.30	50	7.14		
Flows (LPM unless stated)								
13:50:19	160	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		33.91	0.5	0.5	OK	OK	OK	
		13:50:19	160	CO				
				Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
81.18	83.01			6738.28	50	7.14		
Flows (LPM unless stated)								
13:50:19	160	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		33.96	0.7	0.75	OK	OK	ALARM	

FLIGHT NUMBER	B096	DATE:	19/5/05	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: CWVC					

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B096

Date: 19/05/05

Operator: PAPJ

Page 2 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
111048	10		612								RUN@230
1112	10		612								
111447											
112245	15		614								END OF RUN START RUN 2 @200
1124	15		614								
1126	30		614								
1128	15		614								
112902	50		614		40	200	8				END RUN 2 START RUN 3 @105
113725	30		614								
1139	10		614								
1141	14		616								
1142	30		618		400	75	11				END RUN 3 START RUN 4 @ 100
114256											
114741	20		642		400	75	11				
1150	160		648		200	100	11				
1152	6		652								
1154	6		665								
1156	18		666								
120012	35		670								END OF RUN 4 START RUN 5 @ 090
120515	40		680		400	150	12				
1207	100		703		200	100	12				
1209	50		728		200	200	12				
1211	5		739		200	100	12				
121186											END OF RUN 5 START P2.1
121513	10		805		100	100	12				END P2.2 START RUN 6 AND END 2.2
121617	5		811								
121724	6		812								
1219	20		814		100	150	12				
121926	40		819		100	400	1				END 6 AND START 3.1
12											
1221	30		828		500	300	1				

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B096

Date: 19/5/05

Operator: PAPJ

Page 3 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
1223	30	0.5	835		200	200	1				
122332											END OF 7 START P4.1
1224	12	0.5	845		600	200	12				
122432											END 4.1 START 4.2
1225	40	0.4	852		70	200	12				
122543											END 4.2 START 8
1226	40	0.6	860								
122749											END 8
123326	11	0.1	862								START 5.1 @ 090
1235	100	0.3	867		500	300	12				
1236	20	0.09	869								
123634	25	0.1	869								END 5.1 START 5.2
123949											END 5.2 START 9
124311											START 6.1
1244											RUN 10 @140
1250	30	0.09	877								
125055											END 10
125135											START
1252	30	0.09	877								
1253	30	0.09	877								
1255	30	0.09	877								
1301	60	0.09	877								
130616											START 11 @050
1307	100	0.1	953		16	600	1				
											END 11
131154											START 8 @050
131250	50	0.09	955		30	300	1				060
131350	200	0.5	961		200	400	1				070
131451											080 END 8

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B096**

Date: 19/05/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	Y
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS		N
PERCA	Y	N	Bag Sampling		N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B096

Date: 19/05/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off .
2. SID fault-finding during flight.

